

Reproduction of *Donax trunculus* in the littoral of Huelva (southern Atlantic Spain): is there any difference with the Mediterranean population from the Andalusian coast?

Reproducción de *Donax trunculus* en el litoral de Huelva (suroeste Atlántico de España): ¿hay diferencias con la población mediterránea de la costa andaluza?

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Recibido el 13-IV-2011. Aceptado el 11-V-2011

ABSTRACT

The reproductive cycle of *D. trunculus* L., 1758 was studied using histology and changes in flesh dry weight, in the littoral of Huelva (southern Atlantic Spain) from June 1990 to May 1991. The spawning period is essentially synchronic, and extends from February to August, with different individual intensity. Three peaks of spawning have been recorded, April, June and July. The resting period ranges from September to December, with the whole population in cytologized stage in October. The favourable environmental variables, such as high levels of chlorophyll *a* and relatively mild seawater temperatures allow this extensive reproductive period. This cycle shows a diphasic of the spawning period with the Mediterranean population from Málaga, which should imply a different close season for each population.

RESUMEN

Se estudia el ciclo reproductor de *D. trunculus* L., 1758 mediante histología y cambios en la biomasa, en el litoral de Huelva (sur de España Atlántico) entre junio de 1990 y mayo de 1991. El periodo de puesta es básicamente sincrónico y se extiende desde febrero hasta agosto, con intensidad variable según los individuos. Se han registrado tres picos de puesta: abril, junio y julio. El periodo de reposo ocurre entre septiembre y diciembre, con toda la población en la fase citológica en octubre. Las variables ambientales favorables, tales como los altos niveles de clorofila *a* y las temperaturas relativamente templadas del agua permiten un periodo reproductor largo. Este ciclo muestra un desfase del periodo de puesta con relación a la población mediterránea de Málaga, por lo que se recomienda un periodo de veda diferente para cada población.

INTRODUCTION

The overexploitation, for many years, of some marketable shellfish species in southern Spain has mainly been due to an incorrect management of

the fisheries. Until 2003, the law in Andalusia (autonomous region including eight southern provinces of Spain) ruled an extensive close season (over six

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months) for most of the marketable bivalves of this area. Because of the incompatibility of these extensive periods with a profitable economic activity, it was not enforced. The study of the reproduction of the populations of Donacidae in the Mediterranean littoral of Málaga (TIRADO AND SALAS, 1998, 1999) pointed out the possibility of establishing an effective rule with a reduced close season that would still be compatible with profitable fishery activities. These results led regional fishery authorities to promote a research project for the study of reproductive cycles of the most important shellfish, aimed at adjusting the close season to the biology of each species and consequently to improve the management of these fisheries (TIRADO AND RODRIGUEZ DE LA RUA, 2000).

One of the studied species was *Donax trunculus* L. 1785 ("coquina") with a very important consumer market, mostly in the province of Huelva (southwest coast). The reproduction of this species was studied in the Mediterranean littoral of Andalusia (TIRADO AND SALAS, 1998), but it is well known that reproduction in bivalves is strongly related to environmental variables, such as temperature, availability of food or type of beach, among others (BAYNE 1976; BROWN AND MCLAHLAN, 2006). The environmental characteristics of the Atlantic shallow littoral are very different from those of the Mediterranean. The fishing methods are also different, in the Mediterranean littoral the fishery is made by authorized boats, whereas in the Atlantic littoral the fishermen use individual dredges drawn backwards in shallow water. For these reasons, the study of the *Donax trunculus* population from the Atlantic littoral of Huelva was undertaken.

Donax trunculus is a littoral species widely distributed from Brittany (French coast) (LUCAS, 1965; ANSELL AND LAGARDÈRE, 1980; GUILLOU AND LE MOAL, 1980) to Southern Morocco (PASTEUR HUBERT, 1962) and in the Mediterranean (SABELLI, GIANUZZI-SAVELLI AND BEDULLI, 1990). As a com-

mercial species, *D. trunculus* has been intensively studied for fisheries management (BALDACCINI AND BIANUCCI, 1984; FISCHER, BAUCHOT AND SCHENEIDER, 1987), parasitism and predation (RAMÓN, GRACENEA AND GONZÁLEZ-MORENO, 1999; SALAS, TIRADO AND MANJÓN-CABEZA, 2001), population dynamics (MOUËZA AND CHESSEL, 1976; GUILLOU AND LE MOAL, 1980; BAYED AND GUILLOU 1985; MAZÉ AND LABORDA 1988; NEUBERGER-CYWIAK, ACHITUV AND MIZRAHI, 1990; ZEICHEN, AGNESI, MARIANI, MACCARONI AND ARDIZZONE, 2002) and growth and reproduction at different places of the distribution area (LUCAS, 1965; BADINO AND MARCHIONI 1972; MOUËZA AND FRENKIEL-RENAULT, 1973; BAYED 1990; NEUBERGER-CYWIAK ET AL. 1990; TIRADO AND SALAS 1998; GASPÀR, FERREIRA AND MONTEIRO, 1999; DEVAL 2009). All this research has revealed a biological and physiological variability of the populations in relation to environmental factors. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to study the reproductive cycle of *D. trunculus* from Huelva, and to point out the differences between the Atlantic and the Mediterranean populations in order to request the authorities to take into account the biology of the species in a particular area for a better management of the resources.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sampling area is located in the littoral of Doñana (Southwest Spain) (36° 52'N - 6° 26'W) (Fig. 1), in an extensive beach, more than 20 km long and 100-200 m wide, with a tidal range which can reach 3.6 m in spring tides. The beach is of fine grain and gentle slope that can be considered as a dissipative beach (SCHLACHER, SCHOEMAN, DUGAN, LASTRA AND JONES, 2008). The samples were collected, on a sandy bottom at 0.4 m depth, from June 1999 to May 2000, with monthly frequency from October to February and twice a month during the spring and summer months. The specimens were captured

Figure 1. Sampling area. Figure 2. Gear used for commercial collecting of *Donax trunculus*.
 Figura 1. Área de muestreo. Figura 2. Rastro usado para la pesca de *Donax trunculus*.

with a dredge of 45 cm width, with 9 cm long teeth. The mesh was 1.75 cm, usual among the fishermen of the area (Fig 2).

A total of 4333 specimens of *D. trunculus*, between 13 and 44 mm in length, were examined; of these 3798 were used for the analysis of the flesh dry weight variation (about 200 individuals/sample) and 535 specimens for histological study (usually 30 per month).

The length (L) of every specimen was measured to the nearest millimetre, and the soft parts were dried in an oven at 100 °C for 24 h, and weighed to the nearest milligram (flesh dry weight, FDW). Two different indices of condition were applied, FDW/L^3 variation, and that proposed by Crosby and Gale (1990) as $FDW \cdot 1000 / \text{volume of the internal cavity of the shell}$ (considering the millilitres of water as milligrams) which is referred to as CI. The regression of flesh dry weight on the length was calculated for each sample to estimate the variation in biomass of a standard individual, based on the logarithmic transformation of Ricker's function $W = aL^b$ (RICKER, 1975), where W is the weight, L is the length, a is the ordinate at origin, and b is the slope. To minimize the bias introduced by the somatic growth of individuals during the cycle

and by the variation of the size of the specimens between successive samples, the variation of flesh dry weight was estimated for an individual of 29 mm length (mean size of the population studied). For that we took into account the regression lines for every sample.

For histological processing, specimens were anaesthetized with $MgCl_2$, fixed in 10% formaldehyde, embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 10 μm and stained with haematoxylin of Carazzi and eosin, and a trichromic staining (VOF according to GUTIÉRREZ (1967)) of haematoxylin of Carazzi, light green, orange G and acid fuchsine. The stages of development of the gonad were scored according to the scale proposed by DE VILLIERS (1975) for *D. serra* Röding, 1798 in South Africa, who proposed five stages:

Cytolized. The alveoli are very small and wide apart. Some clams can be sexed when a few gametes are present.

Preactive. The alveoli have clearly defined alveolar walls. They are intersected by broad, continuous transverse fascicles. Most clams can be sexed.

Active. The alveoli are large and usually adjacent. The alveolar walls are always complete. Germ cells in various stages of development fill the alveoli

and are both actively increasing and enlarging.

Spawning. The alveolar pattern is disturbed and the alveolar walls are often broken. The alveoli are often flattened and show an orientation towards the centre of the gonad.

Postactive. The amount of germ cells varies, depending on the intensity of spawning and the time that has elapsed since spawning took place. Phagocytic cells are common.

The species showed a sexual differentiation during the time of sexual activity. During the active period, the ovaries of *D. trunculus* are dark blue whereas the testes have a viscous aspects and a whitish-orange colour, which makes possible to identify the sex macroscopically of most of the specimens.

To evaluate the possible influence of environmental factors on the cycle, the temperature of sea water at the surface was measured simultaneously with the collection of the individuals. Samples of water (1l) were taken for determination of chlorophyll *a*. Pigment analyses were carried out by filtering the water through Whatman GF/C glass filters. The pigments of the retained cells were then extracted with acetone for 12 h in cool, dark conditions, following the recommendations of LORENZEN AND JEFFREY (1980). Concentrations of chlorophyll *a* were calculated using the trichromatic equations of JEFFREY AND HUMPHREY (1975).

The test of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Kendal and Pearson's rank correlations included in the program SPSS 8.0, were used to check the distribution of the data. Cross correlation between both condition indexes and percentage of spawning with temperature and chlorophyll *a* levels were calculated to asses their influence on the reproductive cycle.

RESULTS

Environmental factors

The monthly temperature data showed important fluctuations (Fig. 3), with the maximum value in the second

half of September (23 °C) and the minimum (12.5 °C) in December. The most important decrease was recorded from October to November (9.5 °C), and conversely, the highest increase (4.5 °C) was observed from February to the first half of March.

The chlorophyll *a* levels were higher than 2 µg/l throughout the cycle, showing an irregular pattern, with two important peaks, in September (24.3 µg/l) and March (16.1 µg/l).

Sex ratio

The sex ratio was determined on specimens with shell length ranging from 13 to 44 mm. In the samples from December to the end of July it is possible to identify the sex of the whole population according to the colour and external aspect of the gonad. A total of 2564 specimens were examined for sex-ratio study (all the specimens from histology and those of biomass study from December to July), of which 1268 were males (49.45%) and 1296 females (50.55%) (Fig. 4). The sex ratio for all them can be considered as 1:1 ($\chi^2= 0.7$, $P>0.95$). The smallest specimen examined with gonad differentiated was a female of 13.8 mm.

Sexual cycle

Flesh dry weight: The variation of flesh dry weight-length ratio (FDW/L³) during the annual cycle is shown in Figure 5. The mean monthly values of both variables, flesh dry weight (FDW) and size (L³) were considered in 3798 specimens. The standard deviations range between 10 and 21%, being larger than the standard deviations observed in the monthly mean size (between 6 and 15%) (Fig. 6) There is also a broad weight range in most of the samples (Fig. 7), with standard deviation between 23 and 45%.

According to flesh dry weight-length ratio (FDW/L³), the population showed low values during summer and autumn, with an increase from December to February. From February, the flesh dry weight-length ratio decreases until summer, with a

Figure 3. Sea water temperature and concentration of chlorophyll *a* in sea water at the sampling site through the year.

Figura 3. Temperatura del agua de mar y concentración de clorofila *a* en el agua del mar en el sitio de muestreo durante todo el año.

Figure 4. Relative frequency (%) of sexes during the year of study. F: females. M: males.

Figura 4. Frecuencia relativa (%) de los sexos durante el año de estudio. F: hembras. M: machos.

Figure 5. Flesh dry weight (FDW)/ Length (L^3) ratio during the year of study. Bars show standard deviation.

Figura 5. Relación de peso seco de biomasa (FDW)/ Longitud (L^3) durante el año de estudio. Las barras muestran la desviación estándar.

Figure 6. Monthly mean length of shells (L) during the year of study. Bars show standard deviation.

Figura 6. Media mensual de la longitud de las conchas (L) durante el año de estudio. Las barras muestran la desviación estándar.

Figure 7. Monthly mean flesh dry weight (DW) during the year of study. Bars show standard deviation.

Figura 7. Media mensual del peso seco de biomasa (DW) durante el año de estudio. Las barras muestran la desviación estándar.

Figure 8. Index of condition of Crosby and Gale (CI): flesh dry weight \times 1,000 / volume of the internal cavity of the shell, during the year of study.

Figura 8. Índice de condición de Crosby y Gale (CI): Peso seco de la biomasa \times 1000 / volumen de la cavidad interna de la concha, durante el año de estudio.

Table I. Linear regression calculated for each sample. Lm: mean length; flesh dry weight for a standard individual; R²: coefficient of determination; R: coefficient of correlation; N: number of specimens; W: monthly flesh dry weight for a standard individual of 29 mm.

Tabla I. Regresión lineal calculada para cada muestra. Lm: longitud media; R²: coeficiente de determinación; L: coeficiente de correlación; N: número de individuos; W: peso seco de biomasa mensual para un individuo estándar de 29 mm.

	Lm	Regression lines	R ²	R	N	W(L=29 mm)
Jn1	31.22	$y=2.3423x-1.1468$	0.7171	0.8468	200	66.78
Jn2	31	$y=2.2581x-1.0283$	0.8105	0.9003	199	64.46
Jl1	28.15	$y=2.3057x-1.201$	0.8062	0.8979	198	67.15
Jl2	27.37	$y=2.0405x-0.8224$	0.7073	0.8410	200	58.35
A1	26.27	$y=2.3454x-1.2257$	0.8452	0.9193	199	66.79
A2	31.19	$y=2.2428x-1.0357$	0.7991	0.8939	197	64.00
S1	34.57	$y=2.5491x-1.5168$	0.4281	0.6543	202	72.41
S2	27.51	$y=2.3769x-1.2753$	0.9006	0.9490	201	67.65
O	27.81	$y=2.6152x-1.6298$	0.8392	0.9161	199	74.21
N	25.1	$y=2.7123x-1.6903$	0.8741	0.9349	200	76.97
D	25.40	$y=2.701x-1.7035$	0.8329	0.9126	200	76.62
J	27.58	$y=2.8042x-1.7363$	0.9229	0.9607	200	79.58
F	28.69	$y=2.8714x-1.7802$	0.9071	0.9524	200	81.49
Mr1	29.49	$y=2.605x-1.3919$	0.8814	0.9388	199	74.15
Mr2	28.62	$y=2.8325x-1.7953$	0.8816	0.9389	200	80.35
Ap1	27.52	$y=2.785x-1.7727$	0.862	0.9284	199	78.99
Ap2	29.43	$y=2.3754x-1.2251$	0.7727	0.8790	200	67.66
My1	31.09	$y=2.4862x-1.3195$	0.7618	0.8728	202	70.78
My2	29.54	$y=2.4818x-1.3567$	0.8038	0.8965	199	70.62

small peak in May. The CI index showed a similar pattern (Fig. 8). The most important decrease was recorded from March to April.

The monthly regression lines for weight-length relationship are shown in Table I, and the monthly variation of flesh dry weight for a standard individual (W) is represented in Figure 9. According to these data the population from Huelva had a relatively synchronous reproductive pattern, with 18 samples (from a total of 19) explaining 70% of the variations of weight by the length. The pattern of the standard individual was similar to that of CI index.

According to the test of Kolmogorov Smirnov, only the temperature and FDW/L³ data showed a normal distribution. The coefficients of correlation of Pearson and Kendall have been calculated. According to these data, the temperature is inversely correlated with

FDW/L³ ($r=0.541p<0.05$) and with the FDW of the standard individual ($\tau=0.438$, $p<0.01$). No other correlations were significant.

Gametogenic cycle

The data from the histological study are presented in Figure 10. Activation of gonads started in January while the regression began in the second half of August with more than 66% of the population in postactive and cytolized stages. In October, the whole population was in cytolized stage.

During the active period, the histological data showed continuous spawning, with percentages higher than 55% from February to July with three peaks: first half of April (96.67%), June (100%) and second half of July (96.67%), while only 13% of the individuals at the end of August were spawning. Different stages in the same gonad and new activation

Figure 9. Variation in flesh dry weight in a standard *Donax trunculus* animal 29 mm long.
 Figura 9. Variación del peso seco biomasa en un animal estándar de *Donax trunculus* de 29 mm de longitud.

Figure 10. Monthly cumulative frequency of different stages of development of the gonads in *D. trunculus*. C: cytolized; Pr: preactive; EA: early active; A: active; S: spawning; Ps: postactive.
 Figura 10. Frecuencia mensual acumulada de los diferentes estados de desarrollo de las gónadas en *D. trunculus*. C: cicolizado; Pr: preactivo; EA: activo temprano; A: activo; S: en puesta; Ps: postactivo.

without a total regression of the gonad have been observed in many individuals.

The resting period started in September and finished in December. At the beginning of this period, it was impossible to identify the sex of 36% of the individuals, and in October all the individuals were in cytolized stage and it was impossible to identify the sex of 50% of the sample.

DISCUSSION

Sex ratio

The sex-ratio of the population of *Donax trunculus* from Huelva agrees with observations of other authors regarding this species (LUCAS, 1965;

MOUEZA AND FRENKIEL-RENAULT 1973, TIRADO AND SALAS, 1998, DEVAL, 2009, LA VALLE, 2006), but disagrees with the results obtained in the neighbour population of southern Portugal, where GASPARET AL. (1999) found a higher proportion of males in all size classes.

According to the macroscopic identification of the gonads, the active period is more extensive in the Atlantic population, in which it is possible to identify the sex of the whole population from February to the end of July (Fig 3), while in the Mediterranean population, the gonads are coloured in the whole sample only in May and June. Percentages of specimens with non coloured gonads higher than 70% were observed from October to February (TIRADO AND SALAS, 1998)

Sexual cycle

Condition index: The wide range of the standard deviation was partially related to the presence of different stages of development of the gonads. The data for the different condition indexes of this Atlantic population showed a long reproductive period, from December to September, very similar to those found by BAYED (1990) in the Atlantic coast of Morocco and by GASPAS ET AL. 1999 in the South of Portugal, although in the latter there was a continuous decrease of the index of condition from February to August.

However, there are differences with the Mediterranean population of Málaga, in which the most important and continuous decrease of the index of condition was observed from April to June, with an important increase in July. In the population from Huelva, the major decrease was recorded from March to April, with a slight increase in May, but with continuous decrease during the summer.

In Turkey, the population studied by DEVAL (2000) had a shorter reproductive period; the spawning occurred from April to July with a peak between May and June. This reproductive cycle is coincident with that of the population of Málaga. The duration of the reproductive period of the Turkish and Málaga populations was similar to that found in other Mediterranean populations (ANSELL AND BODOY 1979 in Camargue, French Mediterranean coast; MÔUEZA AND FRENKIEL-RENAULT 1973 in Algeria), although these were not coincident in time, due to differences in the environmental variables.

Gametogenic cycle: The data obtained point to continuous spawning for almost the whole population from April to August, coincident with the decrease of the index of condition during this period. The coexistence of different stages in the same gonad, together with a direct transformation from a postactive stage to an active one without the intermediate step of a cytolized stage, have been reported for other donacids (DE VILLIERS, 1975, for *D. serra*; TIRADO

AND SALAS 1998 for *D. trunculus* in Málaga; GASPAS ET AL. 1999 in *D. trunculus* in Faro (Portugal) Tirado and Salas, 1999 for *D. venustus* and *Donax semistriatus*), or other species, such as *Tapes rhomboides* (see MORVAN AND ANSELL, 1988), *Callista chione* (see TIRADO, SALAS AND LÓPEZ, 2002) and *Venus verrucosa* (see TIRADO, SALAS AND MÁRQUEZ, 2003). This renewed activation of the gonad seems to be at the origin of the fluctuations of the indexes of condition during this period. After the most important release of gametes at the beginning of spring, there was new but less intense spawning by the same individuals in the same cycle. The occurrence of successive individual spawnings has also been described in the population of the Adriatic Sea (ZEICHEN ET AL. 2002).

The most important drop of the indexes of condition occurred between March and April, with 100% of the population in spawning, and after an important increase of chlorophyll *a* in March. The strong regression of the gonad from September to October (100% of the population in postactive or cytolized stage) could be related to the strong decrease of the temperature (9.5°C). An inverse correlation has been obtained between temperature and flesh dry weight (FDW/L and FDW of a standard individual). The availability of food in September at the same time as a maximum of chlorophyll *a* could be advantageous for the storage of reserves, after an extensive spawning period. This result is also described in the Algerian population (MÔUEZA AND FRENKIEL-RENAULT, 1973). On the other hand, the increase of chlorophyll *a* in March could be advantageous for the larva after the highest peak of spawning of the population from March to April.

According to the histological data, the Moroccan population of *D. trunculus* have three months of resting period (BAYED, 1990), whereas in the population of Huelva there is only one month (October). Moreover, the percentages of spawning in the population of Huelva are around 100%, whereas in the population of Morocco the percentages never

reach 50%. The data of the population from Faro (Portugal) are more similar to those found in the population of Huelva, although the whole population is never in spawning (maximum 80% in August, GASPARET AL., 1999).

According to SCHLACHER ET AL. (2008) and BROWN AND MCLACHLAN (2006) the populations from dissipative beaches have a more extensive reproductive cycle than those from reflective ones. However, our data on the reproduction of *D. trunculus* from the littoral of Málaga, collected in reflective beaches (TIRADO AND SALAS, 1998)

showed a similar extension of the reproductive cycle to that of the population of Huelva, which lives in a dissipative beach, but with an offset of three months between the beginning of the spawning period in each population. These results justify the necessity of taking into account the biology of the species in a particular area for a better management of the resources by ruling different close seasons for the Atlantic and the Mediterranean populations, from March to April in the Atlantic populations and from May to June in the Mediterranean ones.

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